

LITERATURE REVIEW OF HEURISTIC AND METAHEURISTIC METHODS FOR THE CLP AND ITS PERSPECTIVES FOR THE PHYSICAL INTERNET

Fernando Borges Rangel¹, Vanina Macowski Durski Silva²

^{1,2}Federal University of Santa Catarina,

¹fernandorengel@gmail.com, ORCID: 0009-0002-6369-1737

²vanina.durski@ufsc.br, ORCID:0000-0002-8869-3272

Abstract: *The Container Loading Problem (CLP) represents one of the main challenges in the global logistics chain and aims to maximize the volumetric use of containers, reduce transportation operating costs, increase efficiency, and reduce carbon dioxide emissions. Heuristic and metaheuristic methods used to address the CLP challenge have been widely studied since the 1980s. This article reviews 34 studies published between 2014 and 2024, using the review by Zhao et al. (2014) as a starting point and grouping the approaches into five themes: heuristics, metaheuristics, hybrid methods, multi-objective models with real-world constraints and practical interaction in logistics environments. The review evaluates the volumetric performance of the proposed models, execution times, application maturity, and proposes to discuss its contribution into the concept of the Physical Internet (PI).*

Keywords: *Container Loading Problem, heuristics, metaheuristics, physical internet.*

1. INTRODUCTION

International logistics serves as a competitive advantage by integrating economies and enhancing efficiency, revolutionized by containerization (Christofer, 2001). This standardization introduced the Container Loading Problem (CLP), the challenge of optimally arranging boxes within containers under specific constraints (Can & Sahingoz, 2014; Scheithauer, 2018).

As an NP-Hard problem (Martello et al., 1990), the CLP requires efficient heuristic and metaheuristic solutions and is critical for competitiveness due to its impact on costs and delivery times (Koonsintananan & Kimpan, 2019).

When aligned with the Physical Internet's principles, the CLP gains further strategic importance for building sustainable, interconnected supply chains. This paper therefore reviews CLP solution approaches from the past decade and examines their relevance to the large-scale implementation of the Physical Internet.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE CONTAINER LOADING PROBLEM

2.1 Heuristic approaches

Heuristic methods for the Container Loading Problem (CLP) provide feasible, computationally efficient solutions without guaranteeing optimality (Martello & Toth, 1990).

Significant advances include the work of Liu et al. (2015), who achieved up to 94% volumetric utilization, and Yamashita and Morabito (2015), who incorporated load-stability modeling. Other contributors enhanced performance through improved positioning and equilibrium criteria (Huang, Hwang, & Lu, 2016; Ramos, Oliveira, & Lopes, 2016). A common strategy has been to simplify the 3D problem into 2D subproblems, drastically reducing computation time (Iwasawa et al., 2016; Toffolo et al., 2017). Recent studies continue to push utilization rates higher, with Rajadel Valdés et al. (2022) and Wang et al. (2023) reporting achievements of 90% and 95,2%, respectively, though the latter ignored package weight.

Despite their effectiveness in static scenarios, these heuristics remain limited for dynamic logistics environments like the Physical Internet, where they require adaptation to handle real-time, variable cargo flows.

2.2 Metaheuristic approaches

Metaheuristics are high-level strategies that guide heuristics to find near-optimal solutions for the Container Loading Problem (CLP) by exploring the solution space effectively (Blum & Roli, 2003).

Various approaches have demonstrated success: Can and Sahingoz (2014) used Simulated Annealing to raise utilization from 73,6% to 91,8%, and Li, Zhao, and Zhang (2014) applied a genetic search based on Empty Maximal Spaces, outperforming classical heuristics. Other studies employed Evolutionary Algorithms (González, Miranda, & León, 2016), genetic algorithms for minimizing container count (Menghani & Guha, 2016), and swarm-based optimizations, with Zhou and Liu (2017) and Koonsintananan and Kimpan (2019) achieving utilizations around 92-93%. Recent advances include the Artificial Bee Colony (Phongmoo et al., 2020), iterative refinement methods (Huang et al., 2022), and Multi-population Simplified Swarm Optimization (Truong & Chien, 2024).

While these metaheuristics achieve high space utilization, they are generally complex, sensitive to parameter tuning, and computationally intensive, limiting their suitability for real-time use in dynamic systems like the Physical Internet and rendering them more applicable to offline planning scenarios.

2.3. Hybrid approaches

Hybrid approaches for the Container Loading Problem (CLP) balance intensification and diversification to merge solution quality with computational efficiency.

Studies demonstrate this balance: Remi-Omosowon et al. (2014) achieved near-100% utilization with a fast modular method, while Li and Kaike (2015) integrated differential evolution with a heuristic to outperform classical methods. Subsequent research combined dynamic space partitioning with genetic algorithms (Xiang et al., 2018) and hybrid genetic algorithms with industrial heuristics (Ancora, Palli, & Melchiorri, 2020), consistently achieving high occupancy rates above 90%.

Further advancements include Hybrid Adaptive Large Neighborhood Search (HALNS), which significantly reduced idle space (Li, Chen, & Huo, 2021), and hybrid GRASP, which surpassed static heuristics (Sangchooli & Sajadifar, 2021). Other effective combinations involve Ant Colony Optimization (Zhang et al., 2022) and Tabu Search with gap-filling (Akarsu & Küçükdeniz, 2024). The most recent approach, 3D-MCLP, integrates heuristics with LNS for complex scenarios (Yang et al., 2024).

Overall, these methods represent a promising path for CLP solutions that could be adapted to the Physical Internet if enhanced with intuitive interfaces and standardized protocols.

2.4. Multi-objective approaches and real-world constraints

Multi-objective and real-constraint approaches for the Container Loading Problem (CLP) simultaneously optimize parameters like volume, profit, weight, and stability. Alonso et al. (2014) employed a reactive GRASP meta-heuristic, while González, Miranda, and León (2014) used a layered heuristic to increase container hypervolume by up to 12%. Araya et al. (2020) adapted Beam Search to expand solution quality by 60%, and Gajda et al. (2022) implemented a randomized heuristic with eight real-world constraints, achieving significant cost and CO₂ savings.

These methods are inherently aligned with the Physical Internet's principles by integrating sustainability and operational efficiency. However, their high computational cost remains a barrier to real-time application.

2.5. Practical interaction approaches

Practical interaction approaches for the Container Loading Problem (CLP) are designed for real-time use in industrial logistics. Key developments include an interactive JavaScript interface for manual layout adjustment (González et al., 2014), an online heuristic operating in milliseconds (Ha et al., 2017), and a system incorporating real forklift constraints that increased utilization to 80-90% (Olsson et al., 2020). The most

recent approach by Chien et al. (2024) integrates a genetic algorithm with a neural network for real-time packing that reduces carbon emissions, though it requires substantial computational infrastructure.

Featuring graphical interfaces and equipment integration, these solutions hold the greatest potential for enabling the CLP within the dynamic, collaborative networks of the Physical Internet.

2.6. Physical Internet

Global logistics faces significant challenges, including low load factors below 60% that cause inefficiency and high CO₂ emissions (Montreuil et al., 2012).

In response, the Physical Internet concept proposes to manage goods like data flows, enhancing efficiency and sustainability through integrated physical-digital networks (Ballot et al., 2014). Its implementation relies on three principles: standardized, modular containers (Landeschützer et al., 2015), interconnectivity via open protocols and shared resources (Sarraj et al., 2013), and systemic sustainability (Treiblmaier et al., 2020).

The ALICE group's roadmap envisions global adoption by 2050 but identifies major barriers, including non-standardized nodes, fragmented networks, siloed systems, low adoption incentives, and dispersed governance (ALICE-ETP, 2020).

3. METHOD

The Container Loading Problem (CLP) has been studied since the 1980s, but still lacks scalable industrial applications (Zhao et al., 2014; Chien et al., 2024; Iwasawa et al., 2016). To map heuristic and metaheuristic approaches, a literature review was conducted in Scopus following the PRISMA protocol.

The initial keywords were heuristic, container, and forklift, which yielded 352,179 records in isolation. Cross-referencing reduced the set to 2,032 publications, but only four included all three terms, showing the scarcity of practical solutions. Additional CLP-related terms (e.g., Container Loading, Optimization, Unloading) refined the results to 145. Restricting the time frame to 2014–2024 yielded 76 publications; after duplicate removal and abstract screening, 36 remained, including two reviews (Aydemir & Yigit, 2020; Perumal et al., 2016). Thus, 34 studies were analyzed and grouped into five categories: heuristic, metaheuristic, hybrid, multi-objective/real-constraint, and practical interaction approaches.

For the Physical Internet context, an additional Scopus search combining “Physical Internet” and “Logistics” retrieved 299 records, reduced to 112 after filtering for keyword occurrence. Applying a citation-based criterion, the 20 most cited articles were selected to ensure conceptual maturity and academic recognition.

4. ANALYSIS RESULTS

As highlighted by Zhao et al. (2014), the literature review showed that only 4 of the 34 analyzed proposals evaluated practical container-space-optimization scenarios for everyday business use, representing 11,8% of the publications reviewed (Practical Interaction Models). This lack of empirical studies limits not only the application of heuristic and metaheuristic solution techniques in corporate day-to-day operations but also their integration with disruptive initiatives such as the Physical Internet, which requires algorithms capable of handling dynamic, interconnected cargo flows. Thus, there is a clear opportunity for future research to focus heuristic or metaheuristic approaches on real industrial environments and on how these methods can support other fields of logistics operations research. The Metaheuristic, Heuristic, and Hybrid approaches account for 26,5%, 23,5%, and 26,5%, respectively, while Multi-objective and Real-constraint models were found in 11,8% of the analyzed publications.

In the context of the Physical Internet, the CLP and its approaches are essential parts of the concept. However, although solutions to the Container Loading Problem offer concrete gains such as optimizing container area and volume utilization, eliminating empty routes, reducing CO₂ emissions, and cutting costs, their practical application is still limited. The scarcity of studies developing heuristics and metaheuristics with real-time interfaces and capable of operating in dynamic logistics scenarios highlights precisely the gap between these algorithms and the collaborative digital infrastructure required by the Physical Internet. Without effectively integrated solutions in interconnected systems, it is not possible to fully harness the transformative potential of this concept at large scale.

5. CONCLUSION

This review revealed that heuristic and metaheuristic approaches to the Container Loading Problem (CLP) have evolved significantly over the past decade, achieving notable gains in volumetric utilization, incorporation of real-world constraints, and the use of ever more sophisticated algorithms. Five major solution families were identified: heuristic approaches, metaheuristics, hybrid methods, multi-objective algorithms with real-constraint handling, and real-time interactive methods. Each contributes uniquely to logistics efficiency, whether by maximizing space usage, adapting to multiple operational constraints, or integrating with automated systems.

Despite these advances, only 11,8% of the publications analyzed included practical validations in industrial environments, revealing a critical gap between academic development and operational application. This disconnect not only limits the day-to-day use of CLP algorithms but also their integration with disruptive initiatives such as the Physical Internet, which demands solutions capable of operating in dynamic, interconnected, and collaborative logistics networks.

For the CLP to cease being an isolated optimization problem and become an enabler of the Physical Internet, three strategic directions are essential:

- Development of algorithms (heuristic and/or meta-heuristic) with practical interfaces and real-time operation, enabling operators and automated systems to adjust loading according to changes in the logistics network;
- Adoption of open protocols and interoperable data standards that facilitate the integration of CLP algorithms, logistics platforms, and smart containers;
- Implementation of collaborative pilot projects involving companies, science community and governments to validate the application of the methods in real-world environments and create trust among supply chain stakeholders.

Furthermore, the current barriers to large-scale implementation of the Physical Internet, such as the lack of standardization of logistics nodes, fragmented networks, siloed systems, low adoption by small and medium-sized enterprises, and the absence of unified governance, underscore the urgency of solutions that bridge research and practice. The CLP, when integrated with technologies like IoT, digital twins, and artificial intelligence, can directly contribute to reducing unnecessary routes, lowering CO₂ emissions, and increasing operational efficiency.

Therefore, the convergence between the CLP and the Physical Internet represents not only a technical advance but also a strategic step toward sustainability and global logistics competitiveness. By aligning optimization algorithms with collaborative networks and intelligent flows, it paves the way for a more agile, connected, and efficient logistics system.

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